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Impact Of Quality Leadership Styles On Job Performance Of Lecturers In College Of Education Hong, Adamawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of Lecturers in College of Education, Hong, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The major intention is to find out the leadership styles and the lecturer's level of job performance. This is because there is a general notion that most administrators lack the leadership quality required for effective job performance of subordinates. It is believable that appropriate leadership style will enhance job performance level of the lecturers. Among the many Colleges of Education, the researchers choose College of Education, Hong in Adamawa State as a case study to the research work and the outcome can be generalized. The study is a survey research design. Target population of the study was 864 participants, comprising lecturers of the College. Sample of the study was 282 respondents. The sample was drawn using Taro Yamani's 1967 model. Instrument for data collection was the researcher's structured questionnaire, the instrument has 28 items using Likerts' modified response option of Strongly Agree, Agree(A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential Statistics. The null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 Level Significance using Regression Analysis and the associated ANOVA. Findings of the study revealed that administrative leaders of the college do not employ quality leadership styles to boost the morale of lecturers on job performance. It was recommended that the administrative leaders should endeavor to encourage the lecturers through leadership styles that are capable of stimulating the lecturers to perform job assiduously.

Keywords: Impact, quality leadership styles, job performance.

INTRODUCTION

The existence and success of any organization, institution or establishment depends on the quality and nature of leadership styles. Quality and nature of leadership style is considered important because it is believed to be related to effective job performance of employees. Leaders of organizations are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring sustenance and success of the organizations. Their leadership styles is critical in achieving success or failure. In Colleges of Education, Provosts are the administrative Leaders,

their leadership styles determines performance of Lecturers'. Sofi and Devanadien (2015) defined leadership style as a specific behavior employed by a leader in a company or an institution to empower subordinates to achieve the organization's set goals. Quality leadership styles plays vital roles in enhancing attainment of organizational objectives. The need for leaders to employ quality leadership styles remains. The need assumes that quality leadership is the cornerstone for effective job performance of subordinates.

Impact is effect, it is the influence of something on another. Pearson (2007) described impact as the effect or influence that an event or situation has on someone or something. The impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of employees cannot be overemphasized. There are several leadership styles, Kelechi (2017) enumerated some such as; democratic, autocratic, situational, transactional, transformational, laissez-faire and charismatic leadership styles. Quality leadership style is an acceptable style of leadership. It is the style that gingers, spurs and makes employees more enthusiastic to carry out responsibilities. Quality leadership styles are highly needed in Colleges of Education in order to improve job performance. The implication is that, organizations cannot perform beyond quality of its' leadership.

The job performance decline experienced in most Colleges of Education and other related educational organizations is the prevalence of leaders who lack quality of leadership styles required. Appropriate leadership styles enable workers to perform their job ecstatically. Lack of acceptable leadership styles to encourage subordinates to become more zealous in job performance makes attainment of the desired objectives a mirage. The role of quality leadership styles on organizational performance is enormous. It is a catalyst and source through which objectives and aspirations of an organization becomes realizable. Therefore, it is expected that tertiary education stakeholders and National Commission for Colleges of Education should intensify efforts toward ensuring that administrative leaders employ appropriate leadership styles to encourage lecturers for effective job performance. The most important factor that motivates, energizes, spurs and ignites workers for effect job performance is quality leadership styles. Quality leadership styles implies that the leader is capable of inspiring subordinates to work for attainment of the set out goals. Many College Provosts lack the leadership styles required for effective job performance of lecturers. That makes the lecturers apathetic in performing the expected task, consequent upon poor performance of students in the semester and final year examinations. Kamau (2010) remarked that in many ways, Provosts are responsible for all activities in the College. It is their leadership styles that set the tone of the college, the climate of teaching and learning, the level of professionalism, moral of lecturers and determines what the students may or may not become. This implies that appropriate leadership styles is critical in increasing or decreasing job performance of lecturers. Maicibi (2015) noted that many school administrators lack the leadership styles required for effective performance of subordinates. Quality leadership styles as a construct is not only about exhibition of democratic, situational, participatory or transformational leaderships styles. It is the ability of an administrative leader to establish cordial interpersonal-relationship with subordinates. Workers the world-over desire motivation and mutual interaction. Adequate motivation and mutual interaction influences job performance greatly. But in many organizations, administrative leaders make their office a little paradise, depriving subordinates mutual interaction and that impedes job performance. The essence of quality leadership styles is to energize, stimulates and incite subordinates to work enthusiastically for achievement of goals.

Quality leadership style is highly fundamental in achieving effective job performance. It is the basis through which workers can carry out assignments assiduously. Quality leadership styles is appropriate style of leadership. It pertains to the leaders' administrative fineness. Job performance is accomplishment of the assigned task towards achieving a predetermine goals. Ibukun (2011) referred to job performance as the ability of an administrative leader to manage the human and non-human resources available in the organization with a view to achieving the organizational goals. Quality leadership in the context of the school organization is the ability of the school administrator to spur and incite workers to perform the expected job. Therefore, it is germane and indeed significant that administrative leaders in Colleges of

Education should employ leadership styles that can boost the morale of lecturers to carry out work ecstatically for achievement of the envisaged objectives.

Statement of the problem

It is veracious that in most organizations or institutions, the determinant factor for effective job performance of employees is quality leadership styles. This is because it causes them to be more excited and zealous in carrying out work. Lecturers in Colleges of Education require styles of leadership capable of making them work assiduously. This is because it is believed that quality and nature of leadership styles contribute in the success or failure of an organization.

In College of Education, Hong, job performance of Lecturers is extremely below expectation which led to poor performance of students. This may be due to absence of leadership quality. Effective job performance of lecturers and high performance of students become possible when there is acceptable leadership styles. Unfortunately, steady deterioration in students academic performance is experienced. In view of this therefore, the study examined impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of lecturers in College of Education, Hong.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of lecturers in college of education, Hong, Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically the study intends to:

1. Find out types of leadership styles employed in College of Education, Hong.
2. Ascertain quality of the leadership styles for enhancement of job performance.
3. Find out job performance level of the lecturers.
4. Find out impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of the lecturers.
5. Find out the relationship between quality leadership styles and job performance of lecturers.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the types of leadership styles employed in College of Education, Hong?
2. How qualitative are the leadership styles in enhancing job performance?
3. What is the job performance level of the lecturers?
4. What is the impact of quality leadership styles on job performance of the lecturers?
5. What is the relationship between quality leadership styles and job performance of lecturers?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and tested at 0.05 level significance

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between quality of leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

Significance of the Study

Findings of the study could be gainful to National Commission for Colleges of Education, College of Education Stakeholders, Students, Parents, and Researchers. It will benefit National Commission for Colleges of Education because it will make the commission aware of the prevalence of College Administrators who lack the leadership quality required to make lecturers perform job assiduously and make effort to recruit appropriate leaders. College of Education stakeholders and the entire management of College of Education, Hong could benefit from the study because it will inform them adequately on the need to provide leaders who are sufficiently qualified and possess leadership qualities to lead the lecturers for attainment of goals. Students and parents could gain from the result of the study because as effort is made to provide efficient leaders in the colleges, students will learn better and the unit cost of education incurred by parents will not be a waste. Researchers could benefit from the findings of the study because it will enable them to carry out further research in the related area that could facilitate job performance of lecturers for the realization of goals.

Scope of the Study

The study is delimited to College of Education, Hong, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The major cause of setback or success in realizing the intended goals or aspirations of an organization or institution is leadership style; Leadership style refers to the manner in which organizational leaders manage affairs of their organization. It pertains to the skills and techniques used in leading workers in an organization. Leaders who present inappropriate leadership styles experience failure in realizing the envisaged goals. This is because appropriate leadership style is critical and the cornerstone in enhancing organizational performance and attainment of objectives.

Theoretical Framework

The basic and most fundamental underpinning of democratic leadership theory is participation of subordinates in decision making in an organization for effective performance of organizational chores and attainment of goals. The theory suggests that for an organization to realize the envisaged goals, participation of subordinates in decision making concerning their organization is salient. The theory criticized those who see subordinates as the unfit individuals that can participate in decision making and posits that participation of subordinates in decision making greatly influences their morale and makes them more enthusiastic in job performance. The theory states that participation of subordinates in decision making creates an asset in morale such that when necessary orders are given, the subordinates will respond swiftly and more cooperatively because they participated in making decisions.

The theory emphasized that a good leader should incorporate subordinates in making decisions in order to see the need to make progress and achieve objectives. The theory strongly believed that people who collaborate to do a thing must insist on achieving its goals, and stress that involving subordinates in decision making is not only critical and germane, also that it is a catalyst in facilitating organizational effectiveness. The belief of the theory is that many subordinates possess brilliant ideas that could immensely assist an organization in achieving objectives. The theory has conscientized organizational leaders and lays emphasis on the need for leaders to involve subordinates in decision making. The central idea in the theory is emphasis on involvement of subordinates in decision making for effective job performance and attainment of goals.

Empirical Studies

Duze (2012) conducted a descriptive survey research on leadership styles of principals and job performance of staff in secondary schools in Delta state of Nigeria. Findings of the study showed that democratic leadership style was up ahead of laissez-faire and laissez-faire ahead of autocratic as having a more significant positive relationship with staff job performance in Delta state secondary schools. The study recommended that principals of secondary schools in the state should adopt democratic leadership style in their school administration in order to enhance job performance among teachers and supportive staff which will in turn boost the desired productivity of students and staff. And that the use of autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles which showed low level of job performance should be discouraged in their administration of schools. Similarly, Yusuf (2012) carried out a descriptive survey research on influence of principal's leadership styles on student's academic achievement in secondary schools in Osun state, Nigeria. Findings of the study indicated that democratic leadership style influences student's academic performance positively. That laissez-faire leadership style has no significant positive influence on student's academic performance. The study recommended that education inspectors should regularly visit schools and monitor the administrative works of principals. Also that teaching service boards in collaboration with state ministry of education should be organizing seminars and workshops for school principals on school management. Adeyemi and Bolarinwa (2013) conducted a descriptive survey research on principal's leadership styles on teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ekiti state,

Nigeria. The study found out that democratic style of leadership was the leadership style prevalently used by most secondary school principals in the state. But autocratic leadership style was found to be significantly related to student's academic performance. It was recommended that principals should try to use autocratic leadership style in order to enhance better academic performance of students in their schools. Akparep, Jengre and Mogre (2019) conducted a survey research on influence of leadership on organizational performance at Tuma Kavi Development Association: A qualitative case study of Tamale Northern Region of Ghana. Results showed that there is a strong relationship between democratic leadership style and organizational performance of Tuma Kavi Development Association. It was recommended that leaders should employ democratic leadership style in order to achieve high organizational performance. Badirudeen(2021) carried out a research study on effect of leadership styles on performance of academic staff in Kaduna state university (KASU). Findings of the study revealed that democratic, autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles have significant positive relationship with performance of academic staff of KASU. It was recommended that three leadership styles should be used to stimulate the performance of the academic staff, but more of democratic leadership style than the autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study employed survey research design. Nworgu, (2015) defined research as one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. Target population of the study was 964. This comprised lecturers of the college. Sample of the study was 282 respondents. The sample size was obtained using Taro Yamani's technique for sample size determination. Instrument for data collection was the researchers-developed questionnaire. The instrument was prepared in two parts. Part "A" is on personal information about the respondents. Part "B" is questionnaire items arranged in clusters. The instrument was presented to three research experts in Educational Administration and measurement and evaluation for both face and content validation. The experts were issued with initial draft of the instrument for vetting and necessary corrections. They were requested to examine the instrument with respect to adequacy of the items and suitability of the language used. The corrections and inputs of the experts were effected in the final draft of the questionnaire. In order for the researchers to further determine the reliability index of the instrument, a measure of internal consistency was employed. The instrument was trial-tested on 18 lecturers in college of Education, Zing, Taraba state. The indices was calculated using cronbach alpha reliability technique. The coefficient value of 0.81 was obtained. This indicated that the instrument is reliable. The procedure for data collection was direct delivery of the questionnaire to the respondents by the researchers and four research assistants. The research assistants were briefed on how to establish rapport with the respondents while administering the questionnaire. Data collected from the respondents was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Specifically, the research questions were answered using item by item percentage statistics analysis. The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using regression analysis and the associated ANOVA.

RESULTS

The data collected were presented and analyzed as follows:

Research Question 1: What are the types of Leadership styles employed in College of Education Hong?

Table 1

S/No	Item Statements	SA%	A %	D %	SD%	Remarks
1.	The leadership styles employed are autocratic and situational	147 (52%)	70 (25%)	35 (12%)	30 (11%)	SA
2.	The Leadership styles are mostly qualitative and stimulating	40 (14%)	38 (13%)	70 (25%)	134 (48%)	SD
3.	They employ a mixture of laissez-faire and charismatic Leadership styles	130 (46%)	80 (28%)	30 (11%)	42 (15%)	SA
4.	The Leadership styles employed are transactional and transformational	115 (41%)	92 (33%)	40 (14%)	35 (12%)	SA
5.	The Leadership styles employed are democratic and laissez-faire	122 (43%)	88 (31%)	35 (12%)	37 (13%)	SA
6.	The Leadership styles employed by the College administrators is intimidation and threat.	146 (52%)	88 (31%)	30 (11%)	18 (6%)	SA

It is observable from the responses of respondents recorded on the table above that the College Administrators do employ leadership styles that are not qualitative enough to stimulate lecturers to work assiduously for attainment of goals. The greater percentage of Strongly Agree on the table above is an indication that the kind of leadership styles employed are those that can make the lecturers apathetic in performing their expected tasks.

Research Question 2: How qualitative are the Leadership styles in enhancing job performance?

Table 2

S/No	Item Statements	SA%	A %	D %	SD%	Remarks
7.	The leadership styles are qualitative enough to boost the morale of the lecturers in job performance	49 (17%)	36 (13%)	66 (23%)	131 (47%)	SD
8.	The Leadership styles lack the quality required for effective job performance.	162 (57%)	80 (28%)	10 (4%)	30 (11%)	SA
9.	The Leadership styles are extremely qualitative to make the lecturers zealous in job performance	51 (18%)	33 (12%)	70 (25%)	128 (45%)	SD
10.	The Leadership styles are not up to the standard to spur the lecturers	155 (55%)	74 (26%)	30 (11%)	23 (8%)	SA

The responses of respondents recorded on the table above declared conspicuously that the major cause of inefficiency in job performance of the lecturers is poor leadership quality. The implication is that quality leadership style is the cornerstone for effective job performance of employees.

Research Question 3: What is the job performance level of the lecturers?

Table 3

S/No	Item Statements	SA%	A %	D %	SD%	Remarks
11.	Job performance of the lecturers is extremely below expectation.	110 (39%)	90 (32%)	42 (15%)	40 (14%)	SA
12.	Job performance level of the lecturers is very high	50 (18%)	48 (17%)	74 (26%)	110 (39%)	SD
13.	job performance level of lecturers is far below average	98 (35%)	90 (32%)	44 (15%)	50 (18%)	SA
14.	The level of job performance is relatively high.	120 (43%)	80 (28%)	42 (15%)	40 (14%)	SA
15.	The Lecturers are performing to a reasonable level	110 (39%)	91 (32%)	40 (14%)	41 (15%)	SA
16.	The Lecturers are completely lackadaisical in job performance.	131 (47%)	74 (26%)	38 (11%)	39 (14%)	SA

The notion on the above table is that poor quality leadership styles is highly detrimental to job performance of employees. The need to imbibe quality styles of leadership remains. The percentage of strongly agree and strongly disagree are all in consonant with the fact that the level of job performance of the lecturers is below expectation due to poor quality of leadership styles.

Research Question 4. What is the impact of quality Leadership styles on job performance of lecturer?

Table 4

S/No	Item Statements	SA%	A %	D %	SD%	Remarks
17.	Quality leadership styles motivates lecturers for high job performance	136 (48%)	91 (32%)	30 (11%)	25 (9%)	SA
18.	Quality of leadership styles aggravates job performance of the lecturers.	52 (18%)	40 (14%)	70 (25%)	120 (43%)	SD
19.	The quality of leadership styles makes envisaged objective attainable	163 (58%)	71 (25%)	20 (7%)	28 (10%)	SA
20.	The lecturers becomes more apathetic in job performance due to quality of leadership styles.	50 (18%)	54 (19%)	80 (28%)	98 (35%)	SD
21.	The lecturers becomes more ecstatic and enthusiastic in job performance due to quality of leadership styles.	117 (41%)	86 (31%)	50 (18%)	29 (10%)	SA
22.	Quality leadership styles makes lecturers to be more convenient in job performance.	129 (46%)	94 (33%)	40 (14%)	19 (7%)	SA

The responses of respondents recorded on the table above has indicated conspicuously that quality leadership styles has positive impact on job performances of employees in many organizations. It should therefore be emphasized. The implication is that leaders who lack quality leadership styles will hardly achieve the desired objectives.

Research Question 5: *What is the relationship between quality leadership styles and job performance of lecturers?*

Table 5

S/No	Item Statements	SA %	A %	D %	SD%	Remarks
23.	Quality leadership styles improves lecturers' efficiency in job performance	148 (52%)	90 (32%)	30 (11%)	14 (5%)	SA
24.	Quality of leadership styles makes lecturers more sagacious and zealous in job performance.	154 (54%)	88 (31%)	25 (9%)	15 (5%)	SA
25.	It makes lecturers reluctant in job performance	58 (21%)	37 (13%)	82 (29%)	105 (37%)	SD
24.	Quality of leadership styles weakens the zeal of lecturers in job performance.	62 (22%)	41 (15%)	74 (26%)	105 (37%)	SD
27.	It causes lecturers to feel joyous and perform job rigorously.	121 (43%)	96 (34%)	34 (12%)	31 (11%)	SA
28.	Quality leadership styles stimulates job performance level of lecturers and academic growth of students.	133 (47%)	76 (27%)	43 (15%)	30 (11%)	SA

The responses of respondents recorded on the table above has showed that quality leadership styles are significantly related to job performance of employees. The respondents assumed that quality leadership style is the cornerstone for effective job performance of employees. The greater percentage of strongly agree is a clear indication that quality leadership styles contribute in enhancing job performance capability of workers.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between quality of leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

Table 6:

Analysis of variance of regression on relationship between quality of leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	188.364	13	14.489	113.251	.003
Residual	72.491	132	0.549		
Total	260.855	145			

It is conspicuous according to the F-Value of 113.251 which was significant at .003 that quality leadership styles are significantly related to job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education. Therefore the Null Hypothesis of no significant linear relationship was rejected at $p < 0.05$.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

Table 7:

Analysis of variance of regression on relationship between leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education.

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	461.533	9	51.281	331.275	.000
Residual	319.295	218	1.464		
Total	780.828	227			

The F-Value of 331.275 which was significant at .000 is a glaring indication that significant relationship exist between leadership styles and job performance of lecturers in Colleges of Education. Therefore, the Null Hypothesis of no significant linear relationship was rejected at $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

Findings of the study has indicated clearly that the role of quality leadership styles on job performance of employees cannot be overemphasized. That means the impact of quality leadership on job performance of employees is enormous. Despite that, it is obvious from findings of the study that several school administrators still mixes or purely employs autocratic leadership styles. The finding coincides with the proposition of pagewise (2012) that autocratic leadership styles is effective for new and untrained employees who do not know which task to perform or which procedure to follow in carrying out task assigned to them. The finding is also congruent with the opinion of the Canadian Association of Students Activity Advisers (2014) that autocratic leadership style is effective and should be used when time is limited. The finding of the study is in agreement with the finding of Adeyemi (2010), that teachers job performance was found to be better in schools having principals using autocratic leadership styles than in schools having principals using democratic or laissez-faire leadership styles. Finding of the study is in disagreement with the recommendation of Kelechi (2017) that principals should endeavor to employ appropriate leadership styles in order to boost the level of job performance of employees for attainment of the envisaged objectives.

CONCLUSION

Findings of the study led to the believe that most administrative leaders do employ intimidation and threat on subordinates to enforce compliance. It is expected that appropriate leadership styles should be exhibited to enhance performance of employees to make organizational goals realizable.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on findings of the study, the following were recommended:

1. The College Administrator should employ leadership styles, capable of motivating and stimulating lecturers to work eagerly.
2. There should be adequate interpersonal relationship among the administrator and the lecturers.
3. Leadership style should also be based on arising needs.
4. Mutual interaction and cordial working relationship should be a constant practice among the staff.

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